

Properties of Nonlinear MPC Solutions Illustrated with a Simple Example^{*}

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Abstract: We provide examples on how the non-convexity of the underlying optimization problem can affect the solution to nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC) problems. Using numerical simulations, we show different features of NMPC solutions that illustrate the existence of local minima and their effect on properties such as continuity. It is the purpose of this paper to provide simple examples that can be used to demonstrate all these traits. Furthermore, as the existence of local minima can carry over to the existence of locally optimal active sets, we discuss possible challenges from the perspective of solving the NMPC problem explicitly.

Keywords: nonlinear model predictive control, optimal control, active set

1. INTRODUCTION

The non-convexity of the underlying optimization problem is one of the main challenges arising in nonlinear model predictive control (nonlinear MPC, NMPC). Since linear-quadratic MPC problems result in strictly convex optimization problems under mild assumptions, the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions are necessary and sufficient for global optimality and the solution is unique if it exists. This uniqueness implies important properties such as continuity of the MPC feedback law and the optimal cost function (Bemporad et al., 2002; Seron et al., 2003; Tøndel et al., 2003). NMPC problems with nonlinear dynamics are typically not convex even if the cost function and constraints are (see, e.g., Azhmyakov and Raisch, 2008). Consequently, a solution to the optimization problem may not be unique and local minima may exist. Properties such as the continuity of the optimal cost function value or the control signals are therefore no longer guaranteed, and NMPC problems may lose their inherent robustness (see, e.g., Grimm et al., 2004).

The existence of multiple local minima may carry over to the existence of multiple active sets, where *active set* refers to the sets of constraints that are active for an optimal solution. These active sets are important, e.g., for deriving explicit MPC solutions in the linear case (Gupta et al., 2011; Feller et al., 2013; Oberdieck et al., 2017; Mönnigmann, 2019; Mitze and Mönnigmann, 2020; Mitze et al., 2023). The extension of the explicit solution to nonlinear cases has been investigated ever since the first characterization of the continuous piecewise affine law for the linear-quadratic case (see, e.g., Johansen, 2004; Ulbig et al., 2007; Summers et al., 2010; Domínguez and Pistikopoulos, 2011; Raimondo et al.,

2012; Schulze Darup and Mönnigmann, 2012; Mate et al., 2020). These extensions often approximate the partition of the state space by convex sets. However, the contributions introducing explicit NMPC approaches can differ in how they address the non-convexity. Johansen (2004), e.g., states a central convexity assumption for the presented explicit NMPC approach, but also explains that for an extension to the non-convex case global optimization will be needed. Domínguez and Pistikopoulos (2011) identify non-convexity as a major challenge, and state that solving the necessary optimization problems to global optimality might be possible in the construction of the set of all active sets if carried out offline. Mate et al. (2020) point out at which step of their region-free explicit NMPC approach the use of a locally converging solver might lead to challenges.

Discontinuities or stability issues caused by locally optimal solutions can be handled by warm-starting (see, e.g., Scokaert et al., 1999; Pannocchia et al., 2011). Nevertheless, it is interesting to shed light on how non-convexity can affect the optimal solution and the corresponding active sets. It is the purpose of the present paper to provide simple examples for the effect of non-convexity and to demonstrate which properties of the strictly convex linear-quadratic case are lost. Specifically, we analyze the effect of non-convexity by providing examples of

- (i) disjoint regions in the set of admissible initial states for the same active set
- (ii) multiple local minima resulting for the same initial state with the same active set
- (iii) multiple local minima resulting for the same initial state with different active sets

and, as a result of examples (i)-(iii),

- (iv) non-uniqueness of the NMPC feedback signal and the optimal cost function value, which may result in discontinuities.

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We introduce the NMPC problem class, the treated example, and details of our implementation in Section 2. Examples for the effect of non-convexity on the optimal solution are given in Section 3, which is divided according to cases (i)-(iv). Section 4 concludes the findings.

2. INVESTIGATED SETUP

As a preparation we need to state the problem class, the example, and the implementation setup first.

2.1 Problem statement

We consider the discrete-time nonlinear problem class

$$x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)), k = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (1)$$

with states $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and inputs $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$. We assume $f : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, with $f(0,0) = 0$, to be twice continuously differentiable.

The NMPC problem with horizon N for regulation of (1) to the origin reads

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{X,U} \quad & x^\top(N)Px(N) + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x^\top(k)Qx(k) + u^\top(k)Ru(k) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)), k = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ & u(k) \in \mathcal{U}, k = 0, \dots, N-1, \\ & x(k) \in \mathcal{X}, k = 0, \dots, N-1, \\ & x(N) \in \mathcal{T}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Problem (2) is solved in every time step with the initial state $x(0)$ set to the current state of the system. Weighting matrices $Q \succ 0$, $R \succ 0$, and $P \succ 0$ penalizing states, inputs, and terminal state, respectively, are of the obvious dimensions. Constraint sets \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{U} are assumed to be defined by a finite number of linear inequalities. The terminal set will be chosen as an ellipsoid forming one additional inequality, and we assume there exists a terminal controller $\kappa(x)$ such that the terminal set is positive invariant for (1) with $u(k) = \kappa(x(k))$. Further, we assume f , the terminal penalty, the terminal set, and the terminal controller to meet the requirements for stability as stated in Mayne et al. (2000), A1-A4.

We collect the optimization variables of problem (2), i.e., $X = (x^\top(1), \dots, x^\top(N))^\top$ and $U = (u^\top(0), \dots, u^\top(N-1))^\top$, by $Z = (X^\top, U^\top)^\top$ and introduce the compact formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \min_Z \quad & Z^\top H Z \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & F(x(0), Z) = 0, \\ & G(x(0), Z) \leq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $H \in \mathbb{R}^{N(n+m) \times N(n+m)}$, $H \succ 0$, and $F(x(0), Z)$ and $G(x(0), Z)$ to separate equality from inequality constraints. For formulation (3), let the initial guess for the optimization variables forwarded to the optimizer be denoted by Z_0 . We assume the constraints in $G(x(0), Z)$ to be ordered stage-wise according to

$$\begin{aligned} x(0) &\in \mathcal{X}, u(0) \in \mathcal{U} \\ x(1) &\in \mathcal{X}, u(1) \in \mathcal{U} \\ &\vdots \\ x(N-1) &\in \mathcal{X}, u(N-1) \in \mathcal{U} \\ x(N) &\in \mathcal{T} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

without restriction.

For an initial state $x(0)$, we denote an optimal solution minimizing (3) by $Z^*(x(0))$, or by Z^* for short. Let the indices of all q inequality constraints in $G(x(0), Z)$ be collected in the set $\mathcal{Q} = \{1, \dots, q\}$, and let $G_i(x(0), Z)$ refer to the row of $G(x(0), Z)$ that represents constraint $i \in \mathcal{Q}$. A constraint i is called active (inactive) for an optimal solution Z^* if $G_i(x(0), Z^*) = 0$ ($G_i(x(0), Z^*) < 0$). If not stated otherwise, the term *optimal solution* refers to a locally optimal solution.

2.2 Illustrating example

We use a discrete-time variant of the system presented in Chen and Allgöwer (1998)

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(k+1) &= x_1(k) + 0.1x_2(k) + 0.1(0.5 + 0.5x_1(k))u(k) \\ x_2(k+1) &= x_2(k) + 0.1x_1(k) + 0.1(0.5 - 2.0x_2(k))u(k). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

which is bilinear in $x(k)$ and $u(k)$, as illustrating example throughout the paper. We apply state and input constraints

$$\begin{aligned} -2 &\leq x_i(k) \leq 2, \quad i = 1, 2 \\ -2 &\leq u(k) \leq 2, \end{aligned}$$

for all k , respectively. Following Schulze Darup and Mönnigmann (2012), we choose the weighting matrices $Q = \text{diag}(0.05, 0.05)$ and $R = 0.1$ and use the terminal controller $\kappa(x(k)) = (-1.9198, -1.9198)^\top$ and the terminal penalty matrix P and terminal set \mathcal{T}

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \begin{pmatrix} 5.9353 & 5.2774 \\ 5.2774 & 5.9353 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \mathcal{T} &= \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid x^\top P x \leq \gamma\}, \end{aligned}$$

with $\gamma = 0.0606$ to ensure the required stability properties. The prediction horizon is chosen to $N = 12$.

2.3 Numerical setup

We implemented the NMPC in Matlab using Matlab's nonlinear optimizer `fmincon` with options set according to Table 1, which are fixed throughout all calculations reported in this paper. We vary the initial state on a grid with a fixed step size Δx and specified the respective values in the sections to follow. We sometimes vary the initial guess Z_0 for a fixed initial state as needed to enforce convergence to different local minima. We abbreviate $Z_0 = (0, 0, \dots, 0)^\top$, $Z_0 = (2, 2, \dots, 2)^\top$ etc. by $Z_0 = \mathbf{0}$ and $Z_0 = \mathbf{2}$, respectively. For all solutions, we collected the vector of optimization variables Z^* , the set of active constraints \mathcal{A} , and the corresponding optimal cost function value V^* for comparison.

3. PROPERTIES OF NMPC SOLUTIONS

The following subsections are dedicated to the cases (i)-(iv) listed in Section 1. Every case is visualized, and we

Table 1. Options set for `fmincon`.

option	value
'Algorithm'	'active-set'
'MaxFunctionEvaluations'	10^5
'MaxIterations'	10^5

Fig. 1. Disjoint regions with the same active set. Initial states resulting in an active set $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$ are shown in blue, all other feasible initial states are shown in black.

provide additional information such as the initial guess Z_0 or the active set \mathcal{A} .

3.1 Disjoint regions for the same active set

In linear-quadratic MPC, the feasible set is partitioned by convex polyhedra with pairwise disjoint interiors, where each active set defines a polyhedron, i.e., a convex and thus connected region (Bemporad et al., 2002; Seron et al., 2003). We generated a state space partition for example (5) that mimics such a partition into regions with initial points that have an active set in common by solving problem (3) point-wise on a grid with $\Delta x = 0.05$ for both states $x_1(k)$ and $x_2(k)$, resulting in the non-convex feasible set from Figure 1. The initial guess provided to the optimization algorithm was $Z_0 = \mathbf{0}$ in all cases. A total of 105 different active sets appeared for the initial states on the grid. The initial states that result in the active set $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$ (which corresponds to the terminal constraint) are shown in blue. All other initial states, for which the remaining 104 active sets appear, are shown in black. White spaces correspond to initial states on the grid for which no solution was found.

It is evident from Figure 1 that an active set may correspond to disjoint and thus non-convex regions. We recall a convex and thus connected polyhedron exists in the linear-quadratic case (see Bemporad et al., 2002). We note that disjoint regions also appear for other active sets than $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$. Figure 4 in Section 3.3 will provide additional examples.

3.2 Multiple local minima with the same active set

Figure 2 shows two open-loop optimal solutions for the initial state $x(0) = (1.55, -0.75)^\top$. Both solutions result in

Table 2. Data of the open-loop optimal solutions shown in Fig. 2.

solution	Z_0	V^*	$u^*(0)$	\mathcal{A}
blue	2	1.6538	-1.3218	{73}
orange	-2	2.5923	0.4678	{73}

Fig. 2. Multiple local minima of the optimal control problem with the same active set for the same initial state.

the same active set $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$. These two solutions appear depending on the initial guess passed to the optimization algorithm, which was set to $Z_0 = \mathbf{2}$ and $Z_0 = -\mathbf{2}$ for the blue and orange solution shown in the figure, respectively. When used for NMPC, these two solutions result in different input signals and optimal cost function values (see Tab. 2) for the current time step. Multiple solutions of the optimal control problem may result in discontinuities of the NMPC signal, which will be further discussed in Section 3.4 after introducing optimal input signals and cost function values for a larger set of states.

3.3 Multiple local minima with different active sets

Figure 3 shows three open-loop optimal solutions with three different active sets for the same initial state $x(0) =$

Fig. 3. Multiple local minima of the optimal control problem with different active sets for the same initial state.

Table 3. Data of the open-loop optimal solutions shown in Fig. 3.

solution	Z_0	V^*	$u^*(0)$	\mathcal{A}
blue	2	1.9363	-0.4061	{73}
orange	-2	4.0823	2	{5, 60, 66, 73}
yellow	-10	4.0638	-0.6047	{10, 16, 22, 29, 35, 54, 60, 66, 72, 73}

Fig. 4. Effect of multiple local minima on the state-space partition. Solutions on the left and right result for the initial guess $Z_0 = -2$ and $Z_0 = 2$, respectively. Initial states marked with the same color yield the same active set. Points marked in black correspond to initial states not discussed in the text. The figures show a subregion of the state space region shown in Figure 1.

$(1.6, -1.9)^\top$. These solutions result by initializing the optimization algorithm with the initial guesses $Z_0 = 2$, $Z_0 = -2$, and $Z_0 = -10$ for the blue, orange, and yellow curves in the figure, respectively. For $Z_0 = 2$, only the terminal constraint becomes active, i.e., $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$, yielding an optimal cost function value of $V^* = 1.9363$. The initial guess $Z_0 = -2$ results in the active set $\mathcal{A} = \{5, 60, 66, 73\}$. This is also visible in Figure 3, as constraints 5, 60, 66 correspond to the upper bound on $u(k)$ reached in time step $k = 0$ and the lower bound predicted to be reached for time steps $k = 9$ and $k = 10$, respectively. For $Z_0 = -10$, the cardinality of \mathcal{A} increases, with $\mathcal{A} = \{10, 16, 22, 29, 35, 54, 60, 66, 72, 73\}$ now also consisting of active constraints on state $x_2(k)$ (see Fig. 3). While the optimal cost function value V^* is very similar for $Z_0 = -2$ ($V^* = 4.0823$) and $Z_0 = -10$ ($V^* = 4.0638$), the solution for $Z_0 = 2$ results in a considerably lower minimum with $V^* = 1.9363$ (see Tab. 3).

As a preparation to Section 3.4, we illustrate the effect of multiple local minima on the state-space partition. Figure 4 focuses on a subregion of the state space region shown in Figure 1. We solved problem (3) for initial states on a grid with the finer step size $\Delta x = 0.005$ for this subregion. The figure shows the active sets found for the initial guess $Z_0 = -2$ (left subfigure) and $Z_0 = 2$ (right subfigure). In both subfigures, initial states resulting in an active set $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$ (corresponding to the terminal constraint) are depicted in blue. Initial states colored in orange and yellow result in the active sets $\mathcal{A} = \{6, 73\}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{6, 12, 73\}$, respectively. Note that these latter two active sets imply that, in addition to the terminal constraint, also the lower bound on the input value for $k = 0$ (orange) and $k = 0, 1$ (yellow) is active. All initial states that result in active sets different from the stated three active sets are marked black.

The additional regions that appear in the right subfigure of Figure 4 correspond to active sets that already appeared in other regions in the left subfigure. Just as Figure 1 illustrates that regions of initial states that correspond to an active set may not be connected, Figure 4 illustrates

that active sets may not be unique for a region of the initial conditions.

3.4 Discontinuity of NMPC feedback signal and optimal cost function value

Since Figure 4 shows a single active set as a function of the initial state, it is not evident that multiple local minima may result for the same initial condition. This multiplicity is illustrated for the same region in the state space in Figure 5.

The optimal cost function values resulting for $Z_0 = -2$ (top left) illustrate again that discontinuities can occur even if all states result in the same active set. Compared to the optimal cost function values resulting for $Z_0 = 2$ (top right) we can see different local minima resulting in the same active set also for the blue states, as the overall appearance of V^* looks different for values of $x_2(k)$ smaller than approximately -0.2 in the state-space region shown. For this lifted right part in the top right plot of Figure 5, the local minima resulting in a different active set (yellow and orange regions) do not seem to introduce further discontinuities.

The observations carry over to the optimal input signals depicted in the bottom plots in Figure 5. Both, discontinuity within the blue states in the left plot and between states with $x_2(k)$ smaller and larger than a value of approximately -0.2 is visible.

The results for $Z_0 = -2$ (left subfigures) show further discontinuities inside the blue region. We recall all blue points indicate initial states that result in the active set $\mathcal{A} = \{73\}$. These results therefore show that discontinuities may arise even if the active set does not change. Discontinuities of this type may occur if there are multiple local minima for the problem with fixed active set and the solution jumps between these multiple minima. Note that the region that is shaped like a 'W' in the bottom left plot of Figure 5 yields the same values for u^* as in the bottom right plot, and the values in the two top plots also coincide for this region. Essentially, the solution found with initial guess $Z_0 = -2$ in the two plots on the left jumped to the

Fig. 5. Discontinuity of optimal cost function values V^* (top) and optimal control signals $u^*(0)$ (bottom) corresponding to the solutions in Fig. 4 for initial guess $Z_0 = -2$ (left) and $Z_0 = 2$ (right). The angle of view of the top two diagrams is different from that of the bottom two diagrams for better visualization of the surfaces. Initial states of the same color result in the same active sets. Points marked in black correspond to initial states not discussed in the text.

same local minimum that results for initial guess $Z_0 = 2$ as shown in the right two plots while the active set is constant.

Figure 5 shows the continuity of the MPC feedback signal and the optimal cost function known to hold in the strictly convex linear-quadratic case no longer applies in general if nonlinearities cause non-convexity. We note, however, that the discontinuity of the solutions, especially of the optimal cost function values, does not invalidate stability proofs that are based on a nonincreasing cost function value along time steps k while driving the state $x(k)$ to the origin (see, e.g., Scokaert et al., 1999). The nonincreasing characteristic of V^* can still be guaranteed during closed-loop control by using the previous solution as an upper bound for the current solution and by applying a proper warm-starting for solving problem (3).

4. CONCLUSION

Nonlinear system models in NMPC problems usually cause the underlying optimization problem to be non-convex. This non-convexity can lead to multiple local minima and multiple active sets for the same initial state.

We provided examples for the effect of non-convexity with a simple example that permits to visualize the properties of the NMPC problem and its solution. The examples include the existence of disjoint regions resulting in the same active set, and multiple local minima for the same initial state

with the same or with a different active set. We further showed how non-uniqueness may cause discontinuities in both, the optimal cost function value and the optimal input signal.

Future research should focus on system models with different nonlinearities beyond the bilinear one investigated here. Further, recommendations on adequate solvers or solver settings to avoid challenges such as discontinuities arising from local minima should be elaborated.

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